

Specificity of soil humus substances at ash dumps

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Data on the composition of soil humus substances formed on the surface of ash dumps is extremely scarce, though they occupy large areas in some regions of Russia and other countries. The fly ash is a specific technogenic substrate and it may differ from rocks in properties that are significant for its synthesis and accumulation.

At the same time, establishing the specifics of soil humus formed on a technogenic substrate can help to understand the features of humus formation under specific local conditions, and as a result, identify the contribution of individual factors to the global process of carbon deposition by soils. This information can also help address issues related to restoring disturbed lands.

This study aims to establish the specifics of humus substances in soils formed on unreclaimed areas of 50-60-year-old ash dumps under meadow and forest communities in the southern taiga conditions of the Middle Urals (using the ash dumps of the Verkhnetagilsky and Sredneuralsky power plants as an example). The composition of humus was studied according to [1].

It was found that the humus substances in Technosols with a pH value of <7.0, formed under mixed aspen-birch forests on both ash dumps and in a meadow community dominated by cereals and forbs at the Sredneuralsky ash dump, are characterized by a significantly lower content of extractable substances - humic acids (HA) and fulvic acids (FA) and, accordingly, a higher proportion of humins compared to background sod-podzolic soils.

At the same time, the proportion of individual fractions of humic and fulvic acids in these soils is similar: free and bound with mobile sesquioxides humic acids (HA1) and associated with them fulvic acids (FA1) predominate, and the values of the integrated humus index (Cha:Cfa) do not exceed 1.

In contrast to that, the humus substances of the meadow area Technosols at Verkhnetagilsky ash dump with a pH value >7.0 differ from background soils in all major parameters. They have a high proportion of extractable humus acids, with humic acids prevailing over fulvic acids in the upper horizons and bounded with calcium HA dominating in the fractional composition of humic acids.

Therefore, the characteristics of ash material influence the formation of humus in soils of ash dumps. In slightly alkaline conditions, more humic substances are formed with an increased proportion of humic acids, dominated by related with calcium humic acids. This indicates a more intense incorporation of calcium into the biological cycle. In acidic conditions, which bring soil formation closer to that of sod-podzolic soils, humus formation on ash dumps follows a pattern similar to that found in southern taiga soils.

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References

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